

The Exploration Of Information Communication Technology: Availability And Accessibility Among The Primary School Teachers And Students

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 19, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: November 21, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Educational Technology, Learning Process, Educational Televisions, Radios, Multimedia Projectors</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7339662</p>	<p><i>The study was intended to discover the role of educational technology at the primary school level in the district of Peshawar, Pakistan. The nature of this research study was descriptive. The sample size of the male teachers and female teachers was 220 respectively. The student's sample size was 440. Three dissimilar questionnaires were set for teachers and students for the collection of data. The male teachers have more assess and ability to utilize the IT equipment compared to the female teachers. 29.09% of the male teachers while 8.64% of the female teachers had access to the computers. Only 5% of the students had access to the computers and 98.03% of lack internet facility access. The majority of teachers were not using the existing technology in their teaching-learning process. it is recommended that all primary school teachers may be provided training opportunities to use emerging technologies in classrooms and teach effectively.</i></p>

Introduction

Education means to make required changes in the conduct of a person according to the demands and necessities of its concerned society. The primary school level is a vital period in a child's educational life (Culp, 2005). If a tutor thrives in creating a strong base and makes the whole concept understandable to a child, then in the future the student will be capable to pick up challenging concepts easily. It depends upon a successful productive teaching-learning process. Educational technology plays a significant role in making teaching easy and simple and it saves time and makes difficult challenging things easy for pupils (Basit, 2005). The word technology is derivative of the Greek word 'Technic' which means art or skills and logia means science or study. Consequently, technology means the science or study of an art or skill (Sharma & Sharma, 2009). Using technology and computer science to enable learning as well as its role within education is vital to know as technology plays a central role in daily life. The accessibility, usage, and productivity of technological devices and tools have given an advantage to both students and educators (Earthman, 2004).

Technology utilization has expanded as a pupil with learning disabilities use various technological equipment to support their educational needs, as well as educators, exercise technological instruments to directly address students' needs. Moreover, with the addition of technology and educational tools with lessons or texts, teachers deliver students the chance to expand their learning through diverse forms of media and involve pupil who learns through various cognitive learning styles the chance to remain bonded with information in their way (Fischer, 2008). What technology in the schoolroom eventually offers pupils is the chance to explore autonomy within themselves, while still getting the educational academic support and structure required to prosper within education and make them for real-world proficiencies (Haertel, 1981). Educational Technologies include those materials, techniques, organizations, thoughts, tools, instruments, or machines which shape the teaching-learning process by making it highly purposeful, fruitful, and memorable. However, according to a prominent historian Paul Sattler, the term technology is derived from the Latin word "Texere" which means to weave or to construct. So it does not mean practicing machinery and scientific tools, as we consider but it means any practical art applying scientific knowledge. Information technology has dual sides, i.e. technology as a scientific device and technology as a social process (Hallack, 1990).

Technology as devices represents the use of scientific knowledge to do practical works through association that involves machinery and human resources. On the contrary, technology as a social process is the utilization of scientific and organized knowledge to do applied works using a hierarchically systematic ordered procedure which includes men machines (Halstead, 1974). Educational technology is a complex, inclusive and combined process that involves many things like people, thoughts, processes, devices, and organization design to assess problems. Collin a

famous philosopher mentions that “Educational technology refers to making use of diverse methods and procedures to create a learning experience systematically (Higgins et al. 2005). Galbraith specified that educational Technology is the methodical usability of scientific or other organized knowledge to real-world tasks. Sharma elucidates educational technology as “the area of study that simplifies human learning through orderly use of information technology devices, he further states that using technology in the classroom enables teachers and students to find the new conclusion to daily life problems. Technology helps in education to create a better educational syllabus, learning material, and future products and services. It's really important to integrate technology into classrooms (Sharma, 2001). Information Technology is any computer-based tool used to work with information and support the information-processing need of an organization. These tools include; computers, and software and have the potential to bring changes in education (Iqbal, 2005).

This research work is significant in getting the number data and percentage data of different schools of district Peshawar regarding the usage and availability of technological tools. It is also significant in getting proper responses from different teachers that how can technology usage bring change in teachers' as well as students learning processes. The use of educational technology at the primary school level develops important skills in students and teachers, especially in science subjects. With countless online resources, technology can help improve teaching. Teachers can use different apps or trusted online resources to enhance the traditional ways of teaching and to keep students more engaged. Technology can be used to improve teaching and learning and help our students be successful. Technology can be a “force multiplier” for the teacher. Instead of the teacher being the only source of help in a classroom, students can access websites, online tutorials, and more to assist them. Educational technology improves the teaching-learning process and makes it more effective and process-oriented as well. At the primary school level, students' minds are growing and they are learning new things, so the use of Videos and Internet videos regarding science subjects can make difficult concepts easy for students at the primary school level. Keeping in view the importance of ICT, the current study was conducted to investigate the availability, usability, and usefulness of educational technology and the teacher's ability to effectively use educational technology at the primary school level.

Literature Review

The word educational technology is frequently used substitutable with instructional technology. Nevertheless, mark variation exists between these two; instructional technology is a smaller subject as compared to Educational technology. Instructional technology is the sub-class of educational technology (Khan, 2007).

Seels & Richey, define “the word educational technology is larger than instructional technology for educational represents all sides and features of education’ although the word instructional is confined to ‘teaching and learning problems. While the term instructional technology is repeatedly used as indistinguishable from educational technology, it offers certain modifications that do not exist in the meaning of educational technology (Sen, 2001). The usage of Information Technology in the classroom has left behind the old-style approaches of delivering long tedious lectures. By IT the educators can make thought-provoking audio and pictorial presentations that will keep the students involved and will provide them with a greater understanding of all the ideas (Maqsood, 2012). Information Technology has provided numerous tools and applications that can be utilized by school management and educators to trace the growth and development of each pupil and the fathers or mother can also be informed regularly regarding the progress of their child. This technology might be useful for the tutors in the assistance of students in their weak subjects and offering them some extra care. Consequently, IT has kept the educators from old styles of procedures of keeping student records on registers (Friedmann, 2002).

Present-day students are familiar with applications of computers, tablets, and mobile phones. The information tools can be operated to change this obsession encouragingly by using PCs in schoolrooms for a positive purpose, to watch videos, enhance knowledge, and solve questions and concepts (Arrest, 2002). The introduction of computer-generated schoolrooms and laboratories has entirely changed the old-fashioned classrooms and laboratories and their methodologies. This technology permits the schoolboy to learn detailed and difficult challenging concepts in an easy way and short time. On YouTube, there are various channels for school kids providing the best opportunities for school children to learn in an easy and fun way, so children will not get bored and will take huge interest (Culp, 2005). Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is substantial in primary education since it allows kids to look for the information they want and to establish their results. As school children advance through the school system, they begin to be highly responsible for the process of acquiring and modifying their existing knowledge. A lot of scholars consider that ICT should be thoroughly incorporated into Primary and secondary schools to develop computer literate, and self-determined learners (Higgins et al. 2005).

There are three constituents of change while dealing with Educational Technology – syllabus, technology, and tutors. The task is to bring into line these constituents at the same time as keeping balance. Without stability, it can affect the students and school environment negatively from misuse or overuse, while having a serious matter of concern for the children. Instructors and parents should realize the problems our students will face and support a matured digital

environment (Hussinet al.2012). The use of ICT in the school in Pakistan especially at the primary school level is almost negligible and most school administrations and government officials neglect the importance of ICT at the school level, especially at the primary school level. But over the last few years, a gradual increase has been recorded in most the school regarding the utilization of ICT, and student-centered learning through computers, charts, maps, and projectors have helped students to develop a keen interest and increase their knowledge (Maqsood, 2012).

Primary Schools should utilize varied sources of ICT devices to interconnect, generate, distribute, collect, and arrange the information. Days of old-style teaching are gone when educators had to spend a lot more energy and spend a lot of time using chalkboards to enlighten the minds of a pupil with hard difficult tasks, the chalkboards are replaced by collaborative digital whiteboards, using computers, projectors, videotapes or other tools for increasing and modifying their knowledge during class time .when educators are digitally trained for proper utilization of ICT, such methodology can guide students to develop creative to increase their understandings and modify their knowledge and take it o higher level (UNESCO, 2010).

Objectives of the Study

The key objectives of the study were:

1. To investigate the availability, usability and usefulness of educational technology at primary school level.
2. To explore whether teachers are qualified for the productive use of educational technology.

Methodology

This was a descriptive study in a quantitative paradigm. The investigators visited the schools and spent time with the school teachers, and students, and administered the inquiry form containing questions about technology and its usage among the teachers and students. Certain questions were asked from students and teachers. Thus data were collected from these respondents which were further analyzed. The teachers and students of the primary schools in the Peshawar district constituted the population of this research study.

The total numbers of 220 male and 220 females teachers were part of the study while 440 students were randomly selected indiscriminately as the model of the study. The research was descriptive and quantitative. Data in number form and percentage form was collected. Data from the respondents was collected in number form and percentage form. Two inquiry forms were research instruments used data collection and the instrument was self-constructed. Two important questions were asked from students and teachers:

- i. The availability, usability, and usefulness of educational technology at the primary school level.
- ii. Training of teachers for the productive use of educational technology at the primary school level

Results

The data regarding the accessibility of the male teachers towards educational technologies revealed that fewer percent of male teachers had access to the basic IT educational equipment while the majority of them had access to the basic demonstration utilities/models. The percent of access to the computers, internet facility, LED, projectors, and microphones/speakers were 64%, 20%, 81%, 5%, and 111% respectively. While the percentage of access to the models, flashcards, and maps was 61.3%, 85.9%, and 91.8% respectively as shown in Table 1. The data regarding the accessibility of the female teachers towards educational technologies revealed that fewer percent of female teachers had access to the basic IT educational equipment while the majority of them had access to the basic demonstration utilities/models. The percent of access to the computers, internet facility, LED, projectors, and microphones/speakers were 8.64%, 3.64%, 35%, 4.09%, and 54.09% respectively. While the percentage of access to the models, flashcards, and maps was 70%, 90.9%, and 95.4% respectively as shown in Table 2. The questionnaire regarding the Utilization of Technology by the male teachers revealed that the majority of the male teachers sometimes utilize the basic IT equipment during their teaching. 17.2%, 6.36%, 31.82%, 00% and 47.72% male teachers utilize computers, internet facilities, LED, Projectors and microphones/speakers respectively. While 65.4%, 79.55%, and 90.90% utilize basic demonstration models like models, flashcards, and maps respectively. 81.6%, 77.2%, 59.5%, 0.90% and 43.18% sometimes utilize computers, internet facilities, LED, Projectors and microphones/speakers respectively. While 27.27%, 9.55%, and 8.18% sometimes utilize basic demonstration models like models, flashcards, and maps respectively as shown in Table 3.

The questionnaire regarding the Utilization of Technology by the female teachers revealed that the majority of the female teachers sometimes utilize the basic IT equipment during their teaching. 12.73%, 5.00%, 28.63%, 0.45% and 69.09% female teachers utilize computers, internet facilities, LED, Projectors and microphones/speakers respectively. While 75%, 82.27%, and 93.18% utilize basic demonstration models like models, flashcards, and maps respectively. 70.91%, 60.91%, 65.91%, 2.27% and 23.64% sometimes utilize computers, internet facilities, LED, Projectors and microphones/speakers respectively. While 20.45%, 9.09%, and 6.82% sometimes utilize basic demonstration models like models, flashcards, and maps respectively as

shown in Table 4. The questionnaire regarding the student's Utilization of Technology revealed that the majority of the students sometimes utilize the basic IT equipment during their teaching. 5%, 1.36%, 13.98%, 0.90% and 34.45% students utilize computers, internet facilities, LED, Projectors and microphones/speakers respectively. While 32.4%, 91.81%, and 80.0% utilize basic demonstration models like models, flashcards, and maps respectively. 95%, 98.03%, 86.81%, 99.09% and 64.54% sometimes utilize computers, internet facilities, LED, Projectors and microphones/speakers respectively. While 26.36%, 8.18%, and 20% sometimes utilize basic demonstration models like models, flashcards, and maps respectively as shown in Table 5.

The male teachers were asked questions regarding the training and effect of the utilization of IT equipments on the teaching methodology. 46.81% of the male teachers were trained for the utilization of IT equipment while 53.18% were not trained. 83.63% of the male teachers replied that communications among teachers and students enhanced while 16.36% did not find any significant effect. 50% of the male teachers agreed that IT use in education saves time while 63.18% male teachers teaching skills and performance improved with the use of IT equipment's and 64.09% believed that IT equipment's make concepts clear easily with the utilization of IT equipments as shown in Table 6. The female teachers were asked the same questions like that as the male teachers regarding the training and effect of the utilization of IT equipment on the teaching methodology. 25.45% of the female teachers were trained for the utilization of IT equipment while 75.54% were not trained. 80.0% of the female teachers replied that communications among teachers and students were enhanced while 20% did not find any significant effect. 58.18% of the female teachers agreed that IT use in education saves time while 70% of female teachers' teaching skills and performance improved with the use of IT equipment's and 76.81% believed that IT equipment makes concepts clear easily with the utilization of IT equipment's as shown in Table 7.

Table 1

Feedback of Male Educators Regarding the Accessibility of Educational Technologies

S. No	Technologies	Access	% Accessibility	No Access	% Non-Accessibility	Total
1	Computer	64	29.09%	156	70.91%	220
2	Internet facility	20	9.09%	200	90.90%	220
3	LED	81	36.8%	139	63.1%	220
4	Projectors	5	2.27%	215	97.7%	220
5	Mic/Speaker	111	50.45%	109	49.5%	220
6	Models	135	61.3 %	85	38.6%	220
7	Flash-cards	189	85.9%	31	14.09%	220
8	Maps	202	91.8%	18	8.18%	220

Table 2

Feedback of Female Educators Regarding the Accessibility of Educational Technologies

S. No	Technologies	Access	% Accessibility	No Access	% Non-Accessibility	Total
1	Computer	19	8.64%	201	91.3%	220
2	Internet facility	8	3.64%	212	96.3%	220
3	LED	77	35%	143	65%	220
4	Projectors	9	4.09%	211	95.9%	220
5	Mic/Speaker	119	54.09%	101	45.9%	220
6	Models	154	70%	66	30%	220
7	Flash-cards	200	90.9%	20	9.09%	220
8	Maps	210	95.4%	10	4.5%	220

Table 3

Feedback of Male Educators regarding the Utilization of Technology

S.No	Technology	Regularly	%	Sometimes	%	Never Used	%	Total
1	Computers	38	17.2%	179	81.6%	3	1.36%	220
2	Internet facility	14	6.36%	170	77.2%	30	13.64%	220
3	LED	70	31.82%	131	59.5%	19	8.64%	220
4	Projectors	00	00%	2	0.90%	218	99.09%	220
5	Mic/Speaker	105	47.73%	95	43.18%	20	9.09%	220
6	Models	144	65.4%	60	27.27%	14	6.36%	220
7	Flash-cards	175	79.55%	21	9.55%	19	8.64%	220
8	Maps	200	90.90%	18	8.18%	2	0.91%	220

Table 4

Feedback of Female Educators regarding the Utilization of Technology

S. No.	Technology	Regularly	%	Sometimes	%	Never used	%	Total
1	Computers	28	12.73%	156	70.91%	36	16.36%	220
2	Internet facility	11	5.00%	134	60.91%	75	34.09%	220
3	LED	63	28.63%	145	65.91%	12	5.45%	220
4	Projectors	01	0.45%	5	2.27%	215	97.73%	220
5	Mic/Speaker	152	69.09%	52	23.64%	18	8.18%	220
6	Models	165	75%	45	20.45%	10	4.55%	220
7	Flash-cards	192	87.27%	20	9.09%	8	3.64%	220
8	Maps	205	93.18%	15	6.82%	00	00%	220

Table 5*Feedback of Students Regarding the Accessibility of Educational Technologies*

S. No	Technologies	Access	% Accessibility	No Access	% Non-Accessibility	Total
1	Computer	22	5%	418	95%	440
2	Internet facility	6	1.36%	434	98.03%	440
3	LED	58	13.98%	382	86.81%	440
4	Projectors	4	0.90%	436	99.09%	440
5	Mic/Speaker	156	34.45%	284	64.54%	440
6	Models	324	32.4%	116	26.36%	440
7	Flash-cards	404	91.81%	36	8.18%	440
8	Maps	352	80.00%	88	20%	440

Table 6*Feedback of Male Educators Regarding Efficacy and Training for Proper Utilization of Technology*

S. No	Questions	Agree	%	Disagree	%	Total
1	Are you trained and skilled for proper utilization of IT at school?	103	46.81%	117	53.18%	220
2	The communication between educators and pupils enhances with the use of IT.	184	83.63%	36	16.36%	220
3	Teachers' precious time is saved with the application of It in schoolrooms.	110	50%	110	50%	220
4	Teachers' efficiency and professionalism increase with the use of educational technology.	139	63.18%	81	36.81%	220
5	Problematic and tough concepts are made easy with the use of educational technology.	141	64.09%	79	36.90%	220

Table 7*Feedback of Female Educators Regarding Efficacy and Training for Proper Utilization of Technology*

S. No	Questions	Agree	%	Disagree	%	Total
1	Are you trained and skilled for proper utilization of IT at school?	56	25.45%	164	75.54%	220
2	The communication between educators and pupils enhances with the use of IT	176	80%	44	20%	220
3	Teachers' precious time is saved with the application of It in schoolrooms	128	58.18%	92	41.81%	220
4	Teachers' efficiency and professionalism increases with use of educational technology	154	70%	66	38%	220
5	Problematic and tough concepts are made easy with the use of educational technology	169	76.81%	51	23.18%	220

Discussion & Conclusion

This research study aimed to ascertain educators' attitudes towards the practice of technology at primary school levels. The questionnaire survey revealed that the teachers were positive about the use of technology in their classrooms. They most often use the Internet, Pictures, and Computers. The present research indicates the teachers' role and their productivity to deliver the knowledge to pupils have greatly been changed by the use of IT in schoolrooms. The outcomes of the present research also reveal that teachers consider the utilization of information technology tools in the best interest of students because it saves time and makes things easy and also enhances the relationship between teacher and student. Teachers realize the importance of training for the

actual usage of It tools and consider it in the best interest of teachers as well as students. It was noted that teachers were not properly qualified for the effective utilization of educational technology. The scrutiny of data discloses that a large number of teachers are not utilizing the existing available educational technology. It was also noted that computers, radios, educational televisions, overhead projectors, educational software, film strips, V.C.Rs, multimedia projectors, internet facilities, and flip charts were not available in schools. In the majority of schools, pictures, maps, flashcards, projectors, and charts were found to some degree. It was observed that a high number of the teachers use simply blackboard and some geographic maps frequently in their teaching-learning process. It was noted that teachers were not properly qualified for the effective utilization of educational technology. The scrutiny of data discloses that a large number of teachers are not utilizing the existing available educational technology. It was also noted that computers, radios, educational televisions, overhead projectors, educational software, film strips, V.C.Rs, multimedia projectors, internet facilities, and flip charts were not available in schools. In the majority of schools, pictures, maps, flashcards, projectors, and charts were found to some degree. It was observed that a high number of the teachers use simply blackboard and some geographic maps frequently in their teaching-learning process.

Recommendations

While looking at the conclusions, the scholar makes some recommendations that are listed:

1. Tutors should be properly trained for the appropriate usage of technology in classrooms.
2. Information technology tools such as computers, and projectors internet should be made available.
3. Infrastructure for the accommodation of technological equipment may properly be provided.
4. in all those schools where technology is lacking or missing it may be provided on priority bases.

Future Research Studies

It is suggested that such type of research work regarding the application of IT and its efficacy at higher and secondary school levels should be carried out in district Peshawar.

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